

Research papers

Investigation of the added mass effect and bearing stiffness on the rotordynamics of pump-turbine shaft systems

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ABSTRACT

Pumped-storage hydropower (PSH) is an essential technology for efficient energy storage and plays a vital role in achieving net-zero emission targets. Pump-turbine (PT) units are the most commonly used configuration due to their flexibility and rapid transition between storing and generating energy. These units are typically designed as rigid rotors, meaning their rated and runaway speed is below the first critical speed. To guarantee this condition, it's important to accurately calculate the natural frequencies of the shaft line in operation.

In this paper, the natural frequencies of a PT shaft line are thoroughly investigated through numerical simulation models and validated by experimental modal analysis on a PT prototype which determines that the added mass of the pump-turbine runner also has a significant impact on the entire axis. Furthermore, it is predicted that a low stiffnesses in any of the radial or axial bearings can lead to a substantial reduction in the first critical speed of the rotor.

Furthermore, through wavelet analysis applied to radial displacement sensor data during the start-up phase, the first natural frequency in operation can be identified. This frequency can serve as a health indicator for the entire unit and be integrated into advanced monitoring strategies.

1. Introduction

To address global warming and achieve carbon neutrality, it is essential to develop renewable energy generation [1]. Renewable energy sources such as wind and solar energy are increasingly playing an important role in the global energy structure [2]. However, the intermittent and volatile nature of these energy sources poses a major challenge to grid stability [3–6].

In this context, the energy storage becomes crucial. Nowadays, Pumped storage hydropower (PSH) is by far the most used technology for energy storage, representing 96% of the global utility-scale energy storage [7]. PSH not only has a high round-trip efficiency (RTE), can store energy on a large scale and regulate power supply and demand efficiently, but also plays a vital role in maintaining grid stability and ensuring power balance [8].

One of the critical aspects of ensuring the safe operation of these units is shaft stability [9]. Basically, in hydropower systems, the rotor is designed with sufficiently high natural frequencies to avoid undesirable

resonances, i.e. it has to be assured that critical speeds are much higher than the rated speed. These rotors are also known as rigid rotors [10].

Nevertheless, there are some complex effects that can affect the natural frequencies of the shaft line when considering the real operating conditions. These are for example, the bearing stiffness and its possible directionality and the added mass of the water enclosing the runner. The modal characteristics of a hydro-turbine differ when operating in water versus air [11]. Existing research primarily focuses on the impact of fluid on the dynamic characteristics of the runner [12]. It has been observed that the effect of added fluid mass leads to a decrease in the inherent frequency of the runner, particularly when the runner is fully submerged or constrained by the fluid. In recent years, extensive discussions have been conducted on simplified structures [13–19], and these findings are also applicable to the dynamic analysis of real turbine runners [20–23].

In 2024, Cao et al. extended their research from the runner to the rotor, considering the ‘transfer’ phenomenon of the rotor system's modal shapes while accounting for added mass [24]. That study highlights that the inclusion of added mass is essential for accurate determination of the

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natural frequencies of the system. In addition, for rotating machinery such as pump-turbine, whose rotor system length can exceed 10 m and the load is complex, it is also necessary to consider the influence of gyroscopic effect on modal analysis [25–27]. In other words, when considering the modal characteristics of the pump-turbine system, the rotation speed must be considered.

Scholars have conducted extensive research on the gyroscopic effect. Ma et al. established a dual-disk rotor system model based on the gyroscopic effect, revealing the influence of eccentric phase differences on oil film instability and first/s-mode gyroscopic whipping, providing new insights into the nonlinear dynamic characteristics of rotor-bearing systems [28]. Giannini introduced a computational approach to assess flutter instability in gyroscopic conservative dynamical systems [29]. Presas et al. found that submerged disk-like structures exhibit forward whirl (FW) and backward whirl (BW) modes, and as the rotational speed increases, the frequency gap between these modes becomes more pronounced [30–31]. Zeng et al. explored the effect of the wheel gyroscopic effect on hunting stability by calculating linear and nonlinear critical speeds [32]. Despite these advancements, many studies still rely on simplified one-dimensional models [33] to compute the modal characteristics of rotor systems. However, the main limitation of this approach is its oversimplification, which fails to accurately reflect the true modal characteristics, such as precise mode shapes and corresponding natural frequencies, of complex three-dimensional rotor systems [24]. Therefore, it is necessary to establish a 3D model that closely approximates the real system, so that the research results obtained are accurate.

Existing research primarily concentrates on the effects of added mass on the local dynamic characteristics of the runner, whereas the influence of water added mass on the overall dynamic behavior of the pumped storage unit shaft system has received comparatively limited attention. The shaft system of a pumped storage unit comprises multiple coupled components, including the runner, main shaft, and generator rotor. Consequently, the water added mass may substantially affect the overall dynamic characteristics of the shaft system by modifying the mass distribution and the associated modal coupling behavior. Nevertheless, systematic investigations into the effects of water added mass on the global dynamic characteristics of pumped storage unit shaft remain limited. Therefore, this study aims to address this gap by examining the influence of water added mass on the overall shaft dynamics. Additionally, there is a significant gap in the literature regarding modal analysis that accounts for the gyroscopic effects induced by the added mass and rotational motion of the system. Experimental challenges also hinder the advancement of this field, particularly the difficulty of experimentally determining the rotor frequencies of pump-turbine in operation.

This study uses numerical simulation contrasted with experiment, to improve the existing knowledge on the structural dynamic behavior of the shaft system of pump turbines. In particular, this study investigates the added mass effect of water on rotor frequencies, which represents the main contribution of the work, and also examines the influence of bearing stiffness. In terms of numerical simulation, the finite element software ANSYS is used to analyze the free modes of the pump-turbine rotor. In terms of experiments, through hammer tests, the Frequency Response Function (FRF) is calculated in order to obtain the natural frequencies of the system in air and water.

Finally, this research presents a preliminary analysis of a recorded start-up in turbine and pump mode. The continuous wavelet transform is used to analyze the shaft system displacement signal and to identify the resonance frequency band during the startup process. We suggest that controlling the energy or amplitude on this frequency band could be used as health indicator of the whole unit. The conclusions of this study pretend to provide valuable insights for system design and troubleshooting, helping engineers avoid problems related to natural frequencies and resonances in pump-turbine units, thereby improving the safety, reliability, and stability of the equipment.

2. Theory of modal analysis of pump-turbine shaft system

2.1. Theoretical basis of gyro effect

2.1.1. Dynamic equations of rigid body fixed-point rotation

Euler dynamic equation says that for a rigid body rotating around a fixed point, its dynamic equation in a fixed coordinate system is [34]:

$$\begin{cases} I_1 \dot{\omega}_1 - (I_2 - I_3) \omega_2 \omega_3 = M_1 \\ I_2 \dot{\omega}_2 - (I_3 - I_1) \omega_3 \omega_1 = M_2 \\ I_3 \dot{\omega}_3 - (I_1 - I_2) \omega_1 \omega_2 = M_3 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Among these, I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 represent the moments of inertia of the rigid body about the three principal axes, ω_1 , ω_2 , and ω_3 denote the components of the angular velocity of the rigid body, and M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 correspond to the components of the external torque acting on the rigid body.

From the perspective of energy, the Lagrange function $L = T - V$ (T is kinetic energy, V is potential energy), the dynamic equation of the system is [35]:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}_i} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial q_i} = Q_i \quad (2)$$

For the gyro system, by selecting appropriate generalized coordinates q_i , the motion of the gyro can be described by the Lagrange equation.

2.1.2. The precession law of gyroscopic effect

When a gyroscope is subjected to an external torque \vec{M} , its rotation axis will precess around a fixed point, and the precession angular velocity $\vec{\Omega}$ satisfies:

$$\vec{\Omega} = \frac{\vec{M}}{I\omega} \quad (3)$$

Among them, I is the moment of inertia of the gyroscope about its own axis, and ω is the angular velocity of the gyroscope's rotation. This shows that the precession angular velocity is proportional to the external torque and inversely proportional to the inverse of the angular velocity of rotation.

2.2. Theoretical basis of added mass effect

2.2.1. Definition and calculation of added mass

In fluid-structure interaction, when a structure moves in a fluid, the surrounding fluid will be driven to move due to viscosity and inertia, which is equivalent to adding a part of the mass to the structure, that is, the additional mass [24]. For objects with regular shapes, in inviscid, incompressible fluids, the additional mass can be calculated by potential flow theory. For example, taking a sphere moving at a uniform speed in an infinite fluid as an example, its additional mass m_a is:

$$m_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho V \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the fluid density and V is the volume of the sphere. For objects with complex shapes, the additional mass coefficient C_a can be obtained through experimental measurement or numerical calculation, and then the additional mass $m_a = C_a \rho V_0$ can be calculated, and V_0 is the characteristic volume related to the object.

2.2.2. Effect of added mass on structural dynamic characteristics

After considering the additional mass, the dynamic equation of the structure becomes:

$$(M + M_a) \ddot{u} + C \dot{u} + K u = F \quad (5)$$

Among them, M is the structure's own mass matrix, M_a is the additional mass matrix, C is the damping matrix, K is the stiffness matrix, \ddot{u} ,

\ddot{u} , u are acceleration, velocity and displacement vectors respectively, and F is the external force vector. The existence of additional mass changes the total mass of the structure, thereby affecting the dynamic characteristics of the structure such as the natural frequency and vibration response.

2.3. Basic theory of modal analysis

2.3.1. Basic equations of modal analysis

For a linear vibration system with n degrees of freedom, its dynamic equation is [34]:

$$M\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + Ku = 0 \quad (6)$$

Assuming that the system performs simple harmonic vibration $u = \varphi e^{i\omega t}$, substituting into the above formula we can get:

$$(-\omega^2 M + i\omega C + K)\varphi = 0 \quad (7)$$

This is a homogeneous equation with eigenvalue ω^2 and eigenvector φ . In order to have a non-zero solution, the coefficient determinant must be zero, that is:

$$\det(-\omega^2 M + i\omega C + K) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Solving this equation can obtain the system's n natural frequencies ω_i and corresponding vibration modes φ_i .

2.3.2. Physical meaning of modal parameters

The natural frequency ω_i represents the natural vibration frequency of the system when it is in undamped free vibration, reflecting the stiffness and mass characteristics of the system. The vibration mode φ_i describes the vibration form of the system at the i -th natural frequency, that is, the relative displacement relationship between the degrees of freedom. The damping ratio ξ_i can be obtained through experimental measurement or theoretical calculation, which reflects the energy dissipation characteristics of the system during vibration.

2.4. Shaft system dynamics modeling

2.4.1. Simplified shaft physical model

The shaft system structure of a pump-turbine prototype is complex, and reasonable simplification is required for modeling and analysis. The main components of the shaft system are simplified into equal-section beam units. For example, the shaft is simulated using the Timoshenko beam theory, considering the influence of its lateral shear deformation and moment of inertia. The runner is simplified into a concentrated mass unit and connected to the shaft through a rigid connection. The bearing is simplified into a linear spring-damper unit to simulate the supporting effect of the bearing on the shaft system. According to the actual size and material parameters, the geometric dimensions of each component (such as the length and diameter of the shaft, the radius and thickness of the runner, etc.), material properties (elastic modulus, density, Poisson's ratio, etc.) and connection methods (such as welding, key connection, etc.) are determined.

2.4.2. Derivation of the equation of motion considering gyroscopic effect and added mass effect

Step 1: Derivation based on Hamilton's principle

Hamilton's principle is stated as [36]:

$$\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (T - V) dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta W_{nc} dt = 0 \quad (9)$$

where T is the kinetic energy of the system, V is the potential energy of the system, and δW_{nc} is the virtual work of the non-conservative force.

For the shaft system, its kinetic energy includes the translational

kinetic energy of the shaft, the rotational kinetic energy and the kinetic energy of the runner. When the gyroscopic effect is considered, the rotational kinetic energy includes the gyroscopic term. The potential energy mainly comes from the elastic deformation energy of the shaft. The non-conservative force mainly considers the force of the fluid on the shaft system, which is related to the added mass effect.

By deducing the kinetic energy, potential energy and virtual work of the non-conservative force in detail, and using the variational principle, the differential equation of shaft motion considering the gyroscopic effect and the added mass effect is obtained:

$$(M + M_a)\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + Ku + G\dot{u} = F \quad (10)$$

Among them, G is the gyro matrix, which reflects the influence of gyro effect on the axis system dynamics.

Step 2: Matrix form considering gyroscopic effect and added mass effect

Write the above equation in matrix form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} M + M_a & 0 \\ 0 & I_p \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \ddot{u} \\ \ddot{\theta} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} C & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u \\ \theta \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & G \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} F_u \\ F_\theta \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Among them, u is the linear displacement vector, θ is the angular displacement vector, I_p is the polar moment of inertia of the runner, F_u and F_θ are the linear force and torque vectors respectively.

2.5. The mechanism of gyroscopic effect and added mass effect

2.5.1. The mechanism of gyroscopic effect

Step 1: Effects on the stiffness matrix and damping matrix

The gyroscopic effect changes the stiffness matrix and damping matrix of the shaft system. Taking the two-degree-of-freedom shaft system model as an example, after considering the gyroscopic effect, the stiffness matrix K and damping matrix C become:

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} k_{11} & k_{12} \\ K_{21} & k_{22} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} k_{11} & k_{12} + g_{12}\omega \\ k_{21} - g_{21}\omega & k_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} + h_{12}\omega \\ c_{21} - h_{21}\omega & c_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Among them, g_{ij} and h_{ij} are coefficients related to the gyroscopic effect, and ω is the angular velocity of the shaft system. This change causes the natural frequency and respective mode shape of the shaft system to change.

Step 2: Effects on natural frequency and stability

Theoretical analysis shows that the gyroscopic effect will cause the natural frequency of the shaft system to split. When rotating at high speed, the positive precession frequency increases and the reverse precession frequency decreases. When the reverse precession frequency approaches zero, the shaft system may become unstable, that is, vibration instability at that rotating speed occurs. By analyzing the distribution of the roots of the characteristic equation of the shaft system under the gyroscopic effect, the stability boundary of the shaft system can be determined.

2.5.2. The mechanism of the added mass effect

The added mass varies with the motion of the shaft system in the fluid and is not constant. When the shaft system vibrates with different mode shapes, the motion of the surrounding fluid changes leading to

variations in the added mass coefficient. Therefore, every vibration mode may have different added mass coefficients and different natural frequency reductions when considering the dense fluid that surrounds the runner. This will be discussed in this paper.

3. Numerical model

3.1. Investigated pump-turbine prototype

The pump-turbine prototype under investigation is installed in a hydraulic pumped-storage power plant designed for an operational head of approximately 400 m. The rotating parts of the pump-turbine unit include main shaft, runner, generator and bearings which are shown in Fig. 1. The orange part in sectional view Fig. 1 is the water around the runner which has 7 blades. The key geometric dimensions of the shaft system are shown in Table 1.

3.2. General characteristics of the model

The rated speed of this pump-turbine is 600 rpm. And the rated power is approximately 100 MW as turbine and pump. We focus on the four bearings shown in Fig. 1, namely the upper generator guide bearing (UGGB), the lower generator guide bearing (LGGB), thrust bearing (TB) (which supports the whole weight of the runner rotor system), and turbine guide bearing (TGB). Except for TB which is in the axial direction, the others are in the radial direction. The material properties of the structure and the water surrounding the runner are shown in Table 2. Based on the assumptions of potential flow theory, this study employs an acoustic–structural coupling numerical method implemented in the ANSYS Workbench platform to model and compute the added mass of the water surrounding the runner.

3.3. Grid independence analysis and studied modes

In finite element analysis, the size and distribution of the grid directly affects the calculation accuracy and the reliability of the results. In order to validate the simulation results, grid independence verification is performed. We consider the first four mode shapes found in the simulation model which will be the analyzed ones in this paper. The natural frequencies of the first four bending modes under different mesh sizes are summarized in Table 3. In Table 3, M1, M2, M3, and M4

Table 1
Geometric parameters of the shaft and runner.

Serial number	Parameter name	Value (unit)
1	Total shaft length	11,061 mm
2	Upper shaft diameter	600 mm
3	Lower shaft diameter	750 mm
4	Main shaft 1 diameter	800 mm
5	Main shaft 2 diameter	900 mm
6	Generator rotor diameter	3500 mm
7	Runner inlet diameter	1648 mm
8	Runner outlet diameter	2850 mm

Table 2
Material properties of the structure and the fluid surrounding the runner.

Component	Property	Value (unit)
Structural steel	Young's modulus	2.0×10^{11} Pa
	Poisson's ratio	0.3
	Density	7850 kg/m ³
Water	Density	998.2 kg/m ³

Table 3
Comparison table of natural frequencies of the first four bending modes under different mesh elements.

Number of elements ($\times 10^4$)	M1 (Hz)	M2 (Hz)	M3 (Hz)	M4 (Hz)
5	31.30	53.70	129.65	204.75
10	31.18	53.32	128.88	203.29
20	31.14	53.21	128.63	202.89
30	31.12	53.15	128.51	202.68
40	31.11	53.13	128.46	202.60
50	31.11	53.11	128.43	202.54
60	31.10	53.10	128.40	202.50
70	31.10	53.09	128.38	202.54
87	31.09	53.07	128.35	202.41

represent the first, second, third, and fourth order bending modes, respectively. Fig. 2 is the result of grid independence analysis. The ordinate of Fig. 2 is the relative difference between the natural frequency at a specific grid density and the natural frequency at the densest grid density, and the abscissa is the number of grid elements, taking the first four natural frequencies. As can be seen from Fig. 2, the error

Fig. 1. The structure diagram of the pump-turbine unit.

Fig. 2. Grid independence analysis-Natural frequencies and number of elements.

between the initial grid (5×10^4) and the densest grid is not particularly large. This meets the requirement that the error of two adjacent solutions is between 5% and 10%. Considering these results, the resulting mesh has approximately 600,000 elements.

The mode shape is the specific deformation form of the structure when it vibrates freely at a certain natural frequency. Table 4 shows the mode shape of the pump-turbine at the first four natural frequencies in air and in water. The normalized frequency f^* is equal to natural frequency divided by f_{rated} , being the rotating speed of the unit in normal operating conditions.

$$f^* = f / f_{rated} \tag{14}$$

Table 4
Normalized natural frequency and mode shapes from simulation.

		Mode			
		M1	M2	M3	M4
Air					
	$f^{air1} = 3.11$ Global mode	$f^{air2} = 5.31$ Shaft + Runner mode	$f^{air3} = 12.84$ Runner mode	$f^{air4} = 20.25$ Runner mode	
	$f^{water1} = 3.15$ Global mode	$f^{water2} = 4.89$ Shaft + Runner mode	$f^{water3} = 8.85$ Runner mode	$f^{water4} = 16.66$ Shaft + Runner mode	

Observing the first dry mode (in air), the maximum deformation occurs below the coupling. The maximum deformation of the second mode is concentrated in the middle section of the shaft, close to the TB is located. For the third and fourth modes, the maximum deformation mainly occurs in the connection between the shaft system and the runner.

The first mode represents the global displacement of the rotor, the second mode represents the combined vibration of the shaft and the runner, and the third and fourth modes exhibit larger motion of the runner and therefore they are more affected by the added mass (variation of f^* in Table 4). Qualitatively, it is also interesting to see that the mode shape in air (dry mode) and in water (wet mode) is substantially different when the added mass effect becomes larger.

3.4. Bearings and effects of the rotating speed

This study also investigates the impact of bearing stiffness and rotational speed on the structural modes. Bearings are a critical support for rotor dynamics analyses and as such, a good bearing design is essential to ensure stability of rotating parts.

In modal analysis, it is typically assumed that contacts are linear and bound by default. However, in the context of structural dynamics, the added mass induced by fluid-structure coupling, can significantly alter the vibration characteristics of a structure, including its vibration modes and natural frequencies.

3.5. Numerical modal analysis and start-up analysis

In the numerical simulation analysis, the study process is as follows: First, a free modal analysis is performed, assuming no external loads and free boundary conditions, to extract the natural frequencies and corresponding vibration modes of the structure in an unconstrained state (no effects of the bearings). This analysis provides insights into the free vibration characteristics of the structure. Subsequently, springs are added on the bearing locations, and a constrained modal analysis is performed. The effect of bearing stiffness on the modal characteristics is also studied to evaluate its impact on the vibration mode.

4. Experimental analysis

The comparison with experiment data is a critical step in validating the accuracy of the simulation model. Experimental modal analysis is performed on the pump-turbine unit to determine the modal characteristics, focusing on the natural frequencies of the system shaft. Fig. 3 shows the experimental set-up. Axial and radial impacts were performed on the shaft when the runner was in air (dewatered) and in water. For these tests, two accelerometers were placed on the shaft (Dytran 3006A), in the indicated positions. For the modal analysis, the shaft was impacted with an impulse hammer Dytran 5805A. The signal of a relative displacement sensor, permanently installed on the prototype, was recorded during the start-up of the unit as pump and as turbine.

5. Results

5.1. Natural frequencies of the shaft in air and in water

The data obtained during the experimental modal analysis were analyzed by with a *Frequency Response Function (FRF)* as shown in Fig. 4. FRF are calculated according to classical modal analysis theory [38], where the signal of the hammer is the reference signal. Fig. 4(a) and (b) corresponds to the states of the runner in air (dewatered) and water, respectively. Taking Fig. 4(a) as an example, the upper part is the coherence curve and the lower part is the Bode plot. It can be seen from the Bode plot that when the frequency is 31 Hz, the amplitude shows a local maximum, the phase changes by 180 degrees and the correlation is greater than 0.9, which indicates that this is most likely the first-order

Fig. 3. Experimental set-up, indicating the positions of the sensors, impacts and displacement sensor used for the star-up analysis [37].

Fig. 4. FRF in air and water showing the natural frequencies experimentally. (a) In air, (b) in water.

natural mode of the shaft system.

These frequencies are the first experimental natural frequencies of the rotor in air and in water. The results of the natural frequencies according to the numerical model and experimentation are summarized in Fig. 5. Fig. 5(a) shows the simulation and experimental values of the natural frequency of the shaft system when the turbine is surrounded by air. Fig. 5(b) shows the error of the calculated natural frequency with the simulation model and experiment. Fig. 5(c) shows the reduction of the natural frequency due to the added mass. The specific expressions are as

follows:

$$Error = \frac{abs(f^{sim} - f^{exp})}{f^{exp}} \tag{15}$$

$$f_{reduction} = \frac{f^{water} - f^{air}}{f^{air}} \tag{16}$$

As shown in Fig. 5(b), the error between the simulation and

Fig. 5. (a) Natural frequencies, (b) error of the natural frequency: simulation vs. experiment, (c) reduction of the natural frequency in water compared to that in air.

experimental results remains below 7.13%, except for the second-order mode in water, which shows a larger deviation of 19.84%. This discrepancy may be attributed to two factors. First, the simplified support modeling leads to deviations in the equivalent stiffness, particularly for the thrust bearing. The second-order bending mode in water is dominated by the global bending of the shaft–runner assembly, with peak deformation concentrated in a short shaft segment near the thrust bearing, making this mode highly sensitive to local support stiffness and contact conditions that are insufficiently represented by the equivalent spring model. Second, uncertainties in the modeling of fluid added mass contribute to the error, with a more pronounced effect on the second-order wet mode. Wet modal frequencies are highly sensitive to the actual added mass, which is difficult to reproduce accurately due to the effects of boundary conditions, local flow fields, clearances, and geometric details. Fig. 5(c) further illustrates that, in both simulations and experiments, the natural frequencies decrease significantly when accounting for added mass, with the maximum reduction reaching 31.06%, especially for mode 3 and mode 4. It is worth to notice that the developed numerical simulation model fails to predict the reduction in

the first natural frequency, although this reduction is small. Overall, the conclusion of this analysis is to highlight the substantial impact of added mass on the natural frequencies of the rotor and emphasize the necessity of including it for accurate predictions or for advanced monitoring strategies based on the tracking of the natural frequencies.

5.2. Influence of the bearing stiffness on the rotor modes

This part investigates the impact of varying stiffness on the natural frequency and vibration modes of the pump-turbine shaft system, focusing on the effects when each bearing is individually applied to the model. The stiffness ranges corresponding to various bearing configurations are presented in Table 5. Above the shown limits, the individual

Table 5
Range of stiffness values for the bearings and effects on the shaft modes.

Bearing	UGGB	LGGB	TB	TGB
Stiffness ($\times 10^9 \text{N/m}$)	0–100	0–800	0–800	0–800

stiffness of the bearing has no influence on the results.

By individually adjusting the stiffness of each bearing, the ratio of the natural frequency of each mode to the corresponding natural frequency in the free state (no bearings) is calculated. This ratio is then plotted against the bearing stiffness, as shown in Fig. 6. The figure shows results only up to $100 \cdot 10^9$ N/m, as the effect on the natural frequencies beyond this value, up to $800 \cdot 10^9$ N/m (the maximum simulated value), is very limited.

As observed in Fig. 6(a), the stiffness of UGGB has the greatest influence on the first-order bending natural frequency of the pump-turbine shaft system, followed by the second-order bending frequency. Its impact on the third- and fourth-order bending natural frequencies is relatively smaller. The trend in Fig. 6(b) is the same with that in Fig. 6(a), which will not be reiterated here. As Fig. 6(c) shows, the stiffness of TGB exerts the most significant influence on the first-order bending natural frequency, followed by the second- and third-order bending natural frequencies. The fourth-order bending natural frequency is the least sensitive to changes in the stiffness of the turbine bearing. As illustrated in Fig. 6(d), the stiffness of TB has the greatest influence on the first-order bending natural frequency, followed by the third-order

bending natural frequency. The second-order and fourth-order bending natural frequencies are less affected by changes in the stiffness of TB.

The effect of the bearing stiffness on the mode shapes (see Table 4) is small, and therefore its representation is omitted here. Based on Fig. 6, the following observations can be made: (1) Regardless of the bearing type or mode order, as the bearing stiffness increases, the ‘ratio’ gradually converges to a specific value. This indicates that once the bearing stiffness reaches a certain threshold, further increases have a negligible effect on the natural frequency. (2) The appropriate selection of bearing stiffnesses has a more significant impact on the first-order bending natural frequency compared to high-order modes. Therefore, they are particularly important for critical speed calculations. (3) The influence of bearing stiffnesses on the second-order, third-order, and fourth-order natural frequencies differs between TB (in the axial direction) and guide bearings (in the radial direction). Finally, from these results it can be derived that having very low stiffness in one of the bearings (for example excessive worn bearings) can entrain a dangerous situation for the unit as the first order natural frequency would be decreased to a value close to the runaway speed.

Fig. 6. Relationship between natural frequency and bearing stiffness. (a) UGGB, (b) LGGB, (c) TGB (d) TB (axial).

For the present pump-turbine rotor, a specific stiffness was considered in all the bearings. Several combinations varying the four bearing's stiffnesses were tested. The following values (Table 6) adjust quite well the discrepancy between measured natural frequencies and numerical ones in air and water, as shown in Fig. 1.

To enhance the engineering feasibility of natural frequency as a health indicator, this paper further introduces bearing stiffness degradation simulation and sensitivity analysis to quantitatively characterize the impact of different bearing stiffness variations on the first-order natural frequency. The sensitivity coefficient is defined as shown in (17).

$$S_i = \frac{\Delta f / f_0}{\Delta k_i / k_{i0}} \quad (17)$$

$i \in \{UGGB, LGGB, TGB, TB\}$.

Table 7 is a summary table of the sensitivity coefficients of each bearing to the first-order natural frequency. The results show that the impact of different bearing stiffness degradations on the first-order natural frequency varies significantly. The sensitivity coefficients of TGB and UGGB are 1.39 and 1.02, respectively, significantly higher than those of LGGB and TB. This indicates that the first-order mode is most sensitive to the stiffness changes of the first two types of bearings. Under small-amplitude stiffness degradation ($\leq 20\%$), the change in system dynamic characteristics can be approximated as linear. Therefore, the relative change in the first-order natural frequency is represented as a weighted summation of the contributions of each bearing stiffness variation, calculated as shown in (18).

$$\frac{\Delta f}{f_0} \approx \sum_{i=1}^4 S_i \frac{\Delta k_i}{k_{i0}} \quad (18)$$

Based on this, degradation scenarios such as single critical bearing-dominated degradation, generator-side bearing collaborative degradation, and uniform degradation of all bearings were set up to analyze the natural frequency variation trend under the combined action of multiple bearings. Numerical results show that when the stiffness of a TGB or UGGB degrades by approximately 10%, the relative change in the first-order natural frequency reaches the order of 10%. When multiple bearings simultaneously experience small to medium-sized degradation, the impact exhibits a superimposed but not entirely linear amplification trend. In contrast, the impact of stress bearing stiffness degradation on the first-order natural frequency is relatively limited, consistent with the characteristic that the first-order mode is dominated by lateral bending and the stress bearing has a low degree of involvement. Based on the above analysis, when the relative decrease in the first-order natural frequency exceeds approximately 3%–5%, it can be used as a preliminary early warning reference threshold for system-level early degradation, providing a quantitative basis for monitoring the health status of vertical pump-turbine shaft systems.

5.3. Influence of the added mass, RSI and gyroscopic effect

From Fig. 5(c), it can be seen that the added mass reduces the natural frequency by up to 31.06% for the higher modes, which means that this effect cannot be ignored when calculating the natural frequencies of the shaft. Numerous studies have already considered the effect of added mass on the natural frequency of the runner. For example, Presas et al. found that the water around a disk-like structure could reduce the frequencies up to 50% [30–31]; Eguisquiza et al. compared the frequency of pump-turbine runner in air and water and found that the presence of

Table 6
Assumed values for the simulation.

Bearing	UGGB	LGGB	TB	TGB
Stiffness ($\times 10^9 \text{N/m}$)	2	1	1	2

Table 7
Sensitivity coefficient of each bearing to the first natural frequency.

Bearing	Sensitivity coefficient S_i
UGGB	1.02
LGGB	0.5
TGB	1.39
TB	0.11

surrounding water will greatly reduce the natural frequency of the runner, with a reduction rate of 20% to 50%, depending on the mode shape [39]. Much less studies have been discussed the effect of the added mass in the rotor frequencies. Cao et al. used numerical simulations to calculate the natural frequencies of a pump-turbine rotor system and he found that there is a combined influence of gyroscopic effect and added mass effect on the modal characteristics of the pump-turbine rotor system [24].

In this study, we complement previous studies and we have shown that the added mass effect must be considered not only in mode shapes dominated by the runner but also in those ones involving the whole rotor, which typically occur at lower frequencies.

In addition, this paper presents the calculations of rotor stator interaction (RSI) of the pump-turbine. The combined relationship between the wicket gates and guide vanes of a pump-turbine can theoretically predict the excitation frequency and shape generated by RSI [40]. The equation governing the RSI excitation frequencies and shapes is [40]:

$$mZ_v \pm k = nZ_b \quad (19)$$

Z_v is the number of guide vanes, Z_b is the number of blades, and m and n are the harmonic orders. In the rotating coordinate system, the excitation frequency is $f_{rot} = mZ_v\Omega$, while in the stationary coordinate system it is $f_{stat} = nZ_b\Omega$, where Ω is the rotational speed in revolutions/s and k is the excitation mode shape defined by the number of node diameters. The most critical cases correspond to m and n combinations producing low k , especially in the low-order harmonic range.

Resonance can only occur when the excitation frequency is consistent with the natural frequency of the shaft system and the excitation mode shape matches the corresponding mode [41]. The number of blades in this paper is 7, the number of guide vanes is 16, and the main RSI excitation frequencies and their waveforms are summarized in Table 8.

Furthermore, this paper also studies the influence of the gyroscopic effect on the natural frequencies of the shaft system. Fig. 7 shows the Campbell plot of the natural frequencies of the shaft system as a function of rotational speed, which can be used to identify and avoid potential resonance risks during the design phase of a pump-turbine. Here, FWx represents the x-th FW mode, BWx represents the x-th BW mode, and Torsionalx represents the x-th torsional mode (x is the mode order). The intersection point (brown triangle) of the natural frequency curve of each mode with the one-time rotational frequency line ($\times 1$) corresponds to the critical speed of the corresponding mode. The intersection points (green triangles) of the natural frequency curves of each mode and the RSI (f_{rot}) are points that are very likely to induce resonance. As can be seen from Fig. 7, with increasing rotational speed, the natural frequency of the FW mode increases, while the natural frequency of the BW mode

Table 8
Main excitation frequencies (rotating and stationary point of view) and corresponding excitation shapes.

Harmonic m, n	f_{rot} (Hz)	f_{stat} (Hz)	k
1, 2	160	140	-2
1, 3	160	210	+5
2, 4	320	280	-4
2, 5	320	350	+3

Fig. 7. The natural frequencies of the rotor system versus the rotational speed.

gradually decreases; in contrast, the natural frequency of the torsional mode remains essentially unchanged with rotational speed, indicating that it is less affected by the gyroscopic effect. Furthermore, the first-order critical speed of this rotor system is approximately 2.5 times the rated speed, significantly higher than the normal operating speed range of the unit. However, we should be concerned about the potentially

dangerous operating conditions that may arise at certain low-speed operating points due to RSI.

Fig. 8. Amplitude of the shaft vibrations. Comissioning calculations and experimental tests performed in this paper.

5.4. Comparison with the data calculated during the commissioning of the unit

During the commissioning of the unit, the forced response of the full rotor was calculated with the numerical tools available at that time. The rotor was considered to be radially excited at the runner (bottom) with a constant amplitude force of 981kN over a frequency range of 0–50 Hz. The lateral displacement of the rotor was then calculated just below TB. Fig. 8 shows the response from the calculation performed at that time, compared to the modal analysis tests described in this paper. n^* is the ratio to the rated speed of the unit.

The amplitude observed in the experiments described here is slightly smaller than that calculated one during the commissioning tests, although the excitation point and measurement point is different in both situations. The resonant frequency in the experiments is also lower than the calculated one in the commissioning phase. When the runner is surrounded by water, the frequency decreases further and the amplitude is reduced as well, likely due to the added damping effect of the water. This again highlights the importance of considering the influence of water in such assessments.

Although the runaway speed is far from the first theoretical critical speed, it is worth noting the reduction compared to the original value, which highlights the importance of regularly checking the condition of the bearing and thus their stiffness.

5.5. Transient process analysis-startup

Fig. 9 shows the time-frequency contour plots of the signal recorded by the displacement sensor (see Fig. 3) during the startup process of the unit as turbine and pump. The time-frequency representation is obtained by means of a continuous wavelet transform (CWT). This paper uses a sampling frequency of 4096 Hz and selects the generalized Morse wavelet as the mother wavelet. This wavelet has good time-frequency concentration and adjustable time-frequency resolution, and can maintain time-domain frequency resolution across different frequency bands, making it suitable for extracting signal features under complex operating conditions. By converting the wavelet scale to the equivalent frequency, the energy distribution of the signal in the time-frequency plane is obtained. The squared modulus of the wavelet coefficients is used to characterize the energy intensity of each frequency band, and a time-frequency energy cloud map is plotted in pseudo-color form, thus intuitively reflecting the evolution of signal energy with time and frequency.

On a first sight, both types of start-ups show a similar picture. The

main excitation (rotating speed) goes to the rated speed at the end of the acceleration phase (n^* or $f^* = 1$). Nevertheless, a frequency band around 2.7–2.9 times the rated speed is clearly seen, which may be excited by the third harmonic of the rotating speed. This frequency band, with high modal activity, includes the natural frequency of the rotor considering the added mass, which has been identified in the modal analysis test. In the range of the RSI frequencies (excitation range up to $f^* \approx 20$, see Fig. 7), no clear excitation of the natural frequencies was observed, probably due to a low correlation between radial displacement of the runner and deformation of the shaft (see Table 4).

6. Conclusion

This paper presents an extensive study of the natural frequencies and critical speeds of a pump-turbine prototype. The study uses advanced numerical models which have been validated by experimental modal analysis and contrasted with the information available from the unit commissioning.

The study highlights the importance of including the added mass effect in rotor calculations. Due to its relevance, this effect has been extensively discussed in relation to the runner's natural frequencies, but its influence on the rotor is rarely addressed. Although it may be less significant for the rotor's critical speeds, this study shows that it must be considered for an accurate assessment of the first critical speed, as well as for a correct estimation of the higher-order modes.

A parametric study of bearing stiffness has been performed, leading to two important conclusions. First, as the bearing stiffness increases, the natural frequencies of the shaft line approach an asymptotic value, indicating that beyond a certain threshold, further increases in stiffness have little effect on the natural frequencies. The second conclusion is that the first natural frequency, and hence the first critical speed, is clearly dependent on the bearing stiffness. It is shown that, for all bearings, when stiffness falls below a certain threshold, the first natural frequency decreases significantly. This highlights the necessity of regularly checking the condition of the bearings and, if possible, monitoring the natural frequencies, which can be easily evaluated through proper experimental modal analysis. In fact, a comparison between the current natural frequency and the original value calculated during the commissioning phase shows a slight reduction in the first natural frequency.

The analysis of the start-up as turbine and pump and using a wavelet transform applied to the radial displacement sensor reveals that a frequency band near the first natural frequency is excited by the third

Fig. 9. Contour plot. (a) Turbine startup, (b) pump startup.

harmonic of the rotating speed as the unit approaches rated speed. Although the amplitude is small, since the actual operating condition is far from the critical speed, it demonstrates that the first natural frequency of the rotor in operation can be detected with such a sensor.

To summarize, this paper contributes to the understanding of the effects of added mass and bearing stiffness on the rotor natural frequencies of pump-turbine units. It provides a foundation for more accurate modeling of pump-turbine shafts, with the aim of precisely assessing the safety margins relative to critical speeds. Additionally, it opens the door to advanced monitoring strategies based on tracking natural frequencies as indicators of the overall health of the unit.

Nomenclature

f_{rated}	Rated frequency
n_{rated}	Rated speed
<i>PSH</i>	Pumped storage hydropower
<i>RTE</i>	High round-trip efficiency
<i>FRF</i>	Frequency response function
<i>D51</i>	Displacement sensor 51
<i>FW</i>	Forward whirl
<i>BW</i>	Backward whirl
<i>UGGB</i>	Upper generator guide bearing
<i>LGGB</i>	Lower generator guide bearing
<i>TGB</i>	Turbine guide bearing
<i>TB</i>	Thrust bearing
<i>CWT</i>	Continuous wavelet transform

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jiamin Zou: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alexandre Presas:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Yuejiang Han:** Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **David Valentín:** Visualization, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mònica Egusquiza:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Eduard Egusquiza:** Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

All authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest in relation to the manuscript titled “Investigation of the Added Mass Effect and Bearing Stiffness on the Rotordynamics of Pump-Turbine Shaft Systems” submitted to *Journal of Energy storage*. We confirm that the results and interpretations reported in the manuscript are original and have not been plagiarized.

We certify that we have read and understand the *Journal of Energy storage* conflict of interest policy, and we understand that failure to disclose a conflict of interest may result in the manuscript being rejected or retracted.

We also certify that we have disclosed any financial or non-financial relationship that may be interpreted as constituting a conflict of interest in relation to this manuscript. We understand that this information will be subject to peer review, and we are willing to provide further information or clarification if required.

We confirm that we have no known conflicts of interest that would influence the results or interpretation of the data presented in this manuscript, and we understand the failure to disclose a conflict of interest is unethical and may result in sanctions being imposed on us.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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